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Morphological changes to PVDF thin films prepared by casting method as a result of drying conditions

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Abstract. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is one of the most important materials used in separator technologies. Thin films of PVDF were prepared by the casting method in two different thicknesses: 97.8 μm and 181.2 μm . During the preparation process, the effect of controlled heat removal and drying temperature on the morphological and phase changes of the PVDF thin films was monitored. It was found that a drying time of just 7 minutes in a closed space prevented the crystallisation of the polymer (PVDF_Dc7_A and PVDF_DC7_B). Conversely, long-term drying contributes to the recrystallisation of the surface and the oxidation of the PVDF films, with the presence of minor γ -phase (PVDF_Do_B, PVDF_Dc_B) and major α -phase (PVDF_Do_A). The drying temperature (140 °C) affects the polymer's crystallisation. Spherulitic grains grew from an average size of 8.2 μm (PVDF_Do_A sample) to 82.4 μm (PVDF_Dc_A sample). This growth was conditioned by drying in free space and the formation of an ordered lamellar morphology in the spherulitic grains (PVDF_A_A, PVDF_Do_A). Regardless of their thickness, all polymer films showed a hydrophilic surface with WCA values of 45.3 - 74.4 μm and a superoleophilic surface with GCA values ranging from 3.5° to 11.6°.

1. Introduction

The increasing interest in polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and its copolymer for use in battery energy storage systems is focused on improving properties such as flexibility, environmental friendliness, high halogen and acid resistance, lightness, and good biocompatibility [1]. All of these properties are greatly influenced by the preparation techniques and conditions employed. Techniques such as solution casting, electrospinning, melt processing and high-pressure poling result in different nucleation, growth and distribution of the PVDF crystalline phases. This paper presents an overview of one of the main preparation methods, solution casting, and emphasises the impact of preparation conditions on the resulting crystal phases and overall structure.

This study investigates how drying temperature and preparation environment affect the properties of the final PVDF material. One of the controlled preparation conditions is the drying temperature. Higher values can cause faster solvent evaporation, leading to the formation of

larger spherulites. Conversely, lower drying temperatures correspond with slower solvent evaporation, resulting in a more porous structure with smaller spherulitic grains [2]. The evaporation rate significantly affects the phase distribution of PVDF: a low evaporation rate results in a higher percentage of the β -phase, while a high evaporation rate results in a higher percentage of the α -phase. Fast evaporation can lead to the formation of surface-oriented crystalline structures, while slower evaporation can promote the formation of bulk crystalline structures [3]. Another key preparation condition is airflow, which affects the rate of solvent removal and has a significant impact on morphology. For example, slower drying and airflow can be crucial for the self-organisation of polymer chains in thin films, leading to improved carrier mobility [4].

Controlling the drying conditions is crucial for controlling the final morphology and properties of PVDF thin films prepared using the solution casting method. Understanding how specific conditions affect the properties of final polymer films is necessary for producing materials that meet specific application requirements. This study aimed to investigate the impact of various conditions on the thickness and morphology of PVDF thin films during drying.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 PVDF thin films preparation

The PVDF thin films were prepared using the casting method with 10 ml of N,N-dimethylformamide (Sigma-Aldrich, $M_w = 73.095$ g/mol) and 6.4 ml of acetone (Sigma-Aldrich, $M_w = 58.081$ g/mol) as solvents. The solvent mixture was heated to 80°C for 15 minutes, after which 0.5 g (respectively 1 g) of PVDF granules were added and dissolved at 80°C for 30 minutes.

This procedure was used for all samples, differing only in the following four drying conditions. (1) The solution was poured into a Petri dish that had been heated to 90°C on a hotplate. The Petri dish containing the solution was placed back on the hotplate and dried for 20–30 minutes at 90°C until the solvents had completely evaporated into the surrounding environment (the samples were labelled PVDF_A_A and PVDF_A_B). (2) The solution was poured onto a Petri dish and dried at 140°C for 24 hours in an open fume hood (samples marked PVDF_Do_A and PVDF_Do_B). (3) The solution was poured onto a Petri dish and dried at 140°C for 24 hours in a closed fume hood to ensure evaporation of the solvents (samples marked PVDF_Closed_A and PVDF_Closed_B). No air was supplied to the fume hood. Warm air was specifically extracted from the fume hood (samples marked PVDF_Dc_A and PVDF_Dc_B). (4) The solution was poured onto a Petri dish and dried in a closed hood at 140 °C for seven minutes to ensure the solvents were removed (the samples were marked PVDF_Dc7_A and PVDF_Dc7_B). The Petri dishes were always cleaned with ethanol before the solution was poured.

2.2 Characterization methods

Surface morphology of all PVDF thin films was taken using a JEOL JSM-7610F Plus scanning transmission electron microscope (JEOL, France). The polymer samples were coated with a gold thin film to avoid electrical charging during the observation. An accelerating voltage of 15 kV and a secondary electron detector (SEI) were used in the measurement.

The thickness (t) of the PVDF thin films was measured using a digital micrometre In Size 3101 with a resolution of 0.001 mm and a deviation of 0.001 mm. Each sample was measured six times at random locations. The average thickness of the PVDF thin films was determined by arithmetic mean.

The porosity (ϵ) of the PVDF thin films was calculated using the equation (1) based on values measured by the pycnometer technique. Samples measuring 1x2 cm were immersed in ethanol and left to become saturated for two hours. After this time, ethanol was added to refill the pycnometer.

$$\epsilon = \frac{W_2 - W_3 - W_s}{W_1 - W_3}, \quad (1)$$

where W_1 is the pycnometer weight, W_2 is weight of the pycnometer with ethanol and saturated sample, W_3 is the weight of the pycnometer containing ethanol after the sample has been removed and W_s is weight of the sample [5].

The water contact angle (WCA) and glycerol contact angle (GCA) were measured using a three-point technique at 22 °C, 995 mba and relative humidity 50 %. 0.1 ml of distilled water (glycerol respectively) was deposited onto surface of the PVDF thin films using a micropipette, each drop (0.1 ml) was recorded using a Mitutoyo camera (Tokyo, Japan) and its images were evaluated using Pixel Fox program (Germany). The average WCA and GWA are presented as a mean of 3 measurements per each PVDF film.

The FTIR spectra of the PVDF thin films were measured using the ATR (attenuated total reflectance, USA) technique. The samples were positioned and pressed with a fixing device on a single-reflection diamond ATR crystal. The FTIR spectra were collected using an FTIR spectrometer, Nicolet iS50 (ThermoScientific, USA), with a DTGS detector on a Smart Orbit ATR accessory. The measurement conditions were as follows: spectral region, 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} ; spectral resolution, 4 cm^{-1} ; 64 scans; and Happ-Genzel apodization.

Table 1. The PVDF thin film thickness (t), mean spherulite grain size (S_s) evaluated from SEM measurements, porosity (ϵ) and wettability contact angles (WCA - water contact angle, GCA - glycerol contact angle).

Samples	t (μm)	S_s (μm)	ϵ (%)	WCA (deg)	GCA (deg)
PVDF_A_A	33.8	68.7	83	56.4	4.4
PVDF_Do_A	25.8	8.2	79	74.4	3.5
PVDF_Dc_A	42.6	82.4	80	45.3	5.7
PVDF_Dc7_A	97.8	-	87	69.6	3.4
PVDF_A_B	181.2	76.5	58	54.0	8.6
PVDF_Do_B	119.8	23.2	57	57.8	11.6
PVDF_Dc_B	118.2	69.6	77	51.6	3.5
PVDF_Dc7_B	107.4	-	78	74.1	5.4

3. Results and discussion

3.1 The PVDF morphology, thickness and surface characteristics

Two series of PVDF thin films were prepared using the casting method: one with a thickness of 25.8 - 97.8 μm (series PVDF_A) and one with a thickness of 107.4 - 181.2 μm (series PVDF_B). The thickness of the PVDF thin films varies due to the amount of input precursors, i.e. PVDF beads. The average thickness of the PVDF thin films are given in Table 1.

Morphological images of the PVDF surfaces are shown in Fig. 1 for the PVDF_A series and in Fig. 2 for the PVDF series. In both PVDF thin film series, regardless of the thickness of the PVDF_DC7_A and PVDF_DC7_B samples, no crystalline growth of spherulite grains typical of this semi-crystalline polymer material has been observed. These films are compact, with a smooth surface (PVDF_DC7_A), surfaces are formed by cracks or cavities (pvdf_dc7_b). It can be assumed that the drying time (7 minutes) is insufficient to evaporate the solvent and for crystallization growth.

Figure 1. SEM images of the PVDF_A_A, PVDF_Do_A, PVDF_Dc_A and PVDF_Dc7_A thin films at different magnifications.

The PVDF_A series (Fig. 1), i.e. thin films with a lower concentration of PVDF input beads, exhibited a spherulitic structure with an average grain size ranging from 68.7 to 82.4 μm (Ss). The individual grains were adjacent to each other along their edges, and cavities with an average size of approximately 10 μm were located on the tops of the grains. The spherulitic grains of the PVDF_A_A and PVDF_Do_A thin films formed due to the rapid self-assembly of polymer chains into thin layers, caused by the rapid removal of solvent with rapid air flow. The finest spherulitic grains were detected in the PVDF_Do_A thin film (Ss = 8.2 μm), where the grain tops, which correspond to the rapid air suction during the drying of PVDF films, are also visible together with the

spherulitic lamellae. In contrast, in a closed space where air extraction was controlled, the spherulitic grains of the PVDF_Dc_A thin films were more homogeneous in size and closely adjacent to each other along the entire circumference, with cavities only sporadically present at the edges of the grains. These grains were the largest in size (82.4 μm , Ss) and had a smooth surface with grooves and wrinkles, which arose as a result of surface recrystallisation at a high temperature (140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and over a very long drying time (24 hours).

Figure 2. SEM images of the PVDF_A_B, PVDF_Do_B, PVDF_Dc_B and PVDF_Dc7_B thin films at different magnifications.

In the PVDF_B series (Fig. 2), the spherulitic grains are similar in size to those in the PVDF_A series, but their surface morphology differs significantly. The individual grains are non-uniform in shape, dissected, and closely adhere to each other. Only in the PVDF_A_B thin film, which has an average grain size of 76.5 μm , is the peak of the spherulitic grains noticeable. Conversely, the PVDF_Do_B thin film has the finest grains, with an average size of 23.2 μm . It can be assumed that surface oxidation of the polymer occurs in the case of an open space when the air extraction is not regulated, which is manifested by the formation of fine scales on the surfaces of the spherulitic grains. This can also be confirmed by the lower porosity values (ϵ), which reach only 58% and 57% in the PVDF_A_B and PVDF_Do_B thin films, respectively. In the case of regulated air and heat extraction, i.e. in a closed space, the polymer scale content is lower, occurring at the edges of the spherulitic grains. The porosity reaches 77% and 78%. In the case of the PVDF_B series, where the highest amount of PVDF beads is used, surface recrystallisation of the polymer occurs predominantly rather than bulk recrystallisation. In this case, the method of heat removal and the temperature during drying have no effect on the morphology of PVDF thin films.

All of the PVDF thin films demonstrated a hydrophilic surface, as defined by water contact angle (WCA) analysis in the range of 45.3 $^{\circ}$ –74.4 $^{\circ}$. The PVDF_Do_A thin film had the highest WCA

value of 74.4° , the smallest film thickness of 25.8 microns (t) and the finest spherulitic structure with an average grain size of 8.2 microns (S_s).

Conversely, the superoleophilic surface was measured using glycerol, with contact angles (GCAs) ranging from 3.5° to 11.6° . The highest GCA value (11.6°) was measured for the PVDF_Do_B thin film, which exhibited a fine spherulitic grain structure ($S_s = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$) and the lowest porosity ($\varepsilon = 57\%$), preventing glycerin droplets from penetrating the polymer matrix [6].

3.2 FTIR analysis of the PVDF films

PVDF is known to exist in three primary polymorphic forms [7]. FTIR spectroscopy is a reliable method for characterizing these structures and distinguishing between the different crystalline phases.

The FTIR spectrum of the thin film PVDF_A_A (Fig. 3) shows typical bands for α -phase, which is predominantly determined by bands at 763 and 614 cm^{-1} attributed to CF_2 bending and skeletal bending vibrations [8,9].

In the spectra of other films, additional peaks typical for the γ -phase appear at positions 1231 , 840 and 510 cm^{-1} , which correspond to C-F out of plane deformation vibration, CH_2 rocking vibration and CF_2 bending vibration, respectively [8,9]. The most significant contribution of this phase can be seen in the spectrum of sample PVDF_Do_A.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of the PVDF_A_A, PVDF_Do_A, PVDF_Dc_A and PVDF_Dc7_A thin films.

Unlike the samples evaluated from area A, the situation in FTIR spectra for the samples from area B is different (Fig. 4). The PVDF_A_B sample already contains a small amount of γ -phase, as well as PVDF_Dc7_B (based on peaks at 840 and 510 cm^{-1}). More of this phase, according to the

intensity of the corresponding peaks, can be observed in the PVDF_Do_B sample. On the contrary, the α -phase prevails in the PVDF_Dc_B sample.

It is therefore clear from the FTIR spectra that the method of film preparation influences the resulting structure of PVDF thin films.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra of the PVDF_A_B, PVDF_Do_B, PVDF_Dc_B and PVDF_Dc7_B thin films.

4. Conclusion

Two series of PVDF thin films were prepared by the casting method. Differences in film thickness and morphological changes were achieved by controlling the removal of heat and the drying temperature during the preparation process. It was demonstrated that the drying temperature influences the rate of solvent evaporation and affects polymer crystallisation, subsequently impacting the size and morphology of spherulitic grains. Meanwhile, controlling heat removal contributes to the self-assembly of polymer chains within the thin films. This is an important attribute for using these polymers as separators in batteries or as membrane separators for water or gas purification. In summary, controlling the drying conditions is essential for tailoring the morphology and properties of PVDF thin films prepared by the casting method, enabling the development of films with the desired characteristics for a range of applications.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15689704>.

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